

FEATURES OF PRINCIPLES AND APPROACHES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A DYNAMIC MODEL

Yuldashev Rustam Elmurodovich

Researcher of the Karshi State University

Annotation. This article examines experience in the characteristics of principles and approaches in the development of the dynamic model of masters.

Key words: principle, synergetic, education, master, profession, personality, research, dynamics, model.

It is important to identify the preliminary theoretical model for the development of a dynamic model of masters, primarily determination of the methodological approaches of system modeling. It is advisable to use the Integrative approach in the substantiation and development of masters, taking into account the complexity and multifaceting process. In particular, the integration of the modeled system, based on systematic, competent, person-oriented and synerdiscus approaches, we believe that the integration of the modeled system.

A systematic approach is applied in the study of complex objects, at which the system of masters is one of these facilities. This approach allows disclosure of relations between the components of the system and increase their effectiveness. It is based on the following principles:

- The principle of integrity is reflecting the connection of each element within the whole system;
- compiled - the location of the system elements within a particular organizational structure and determines the analysis of their relations;
- The principle of hierarchicality - three aspects of the object: the independent system, one of the elements of the high-level system and a system of lower levels of systems;

- The principle of history is reflect the need to consider in the dynamics of development of the system and require the study of previous experiences.

Based on these principles, it is necessary to consider the master's degree as a constantly changing dynamic system consisting of higher education and a constant changes in various components. In the face of the pedagogical look: Goal, content, technological and diagnostic and diagnostic and diagnostic stations are key. In order to increase the effectiveness of the training of masters, it is necessary to pay special attention to the modeling of masters to increase the efficiency of masters and their interaction has been interacted.

In recent years, in the end of primary education, the ideas of education are being promoted and implemented through competencies through competencies. This demonstrates considering the preparation of masters based on a competent approach.

Today, knowledge shows that people should be mastered from people without being transferred to people, but also in personal career.

It is known that without forming skills and skills, knowledge cannot be used, and without them we cannot solve the problem of preparing Master's future professional career. The purpose of education is not only the knowledge and skills, but also to form support competent qualities, support competitions that need students to prepare students for modern society. The competent approach focuses on education and the result is not the amount of information learned, but the ability to act in different situations. This approach is due to the fact that the main focus is on teaching and educational content to the student and the expected results of education. The purpose of the competent approach is to provide the quality of education, which depends on modern needs and values, and reflecting its ideas about the future. [2]. As a result of the application of a competent approach, we have graduates forming specific competencies, which can determine the level of professional activities and the readiness [1].

The most important situation in the professional activity of the teacher is the research competency, in the second phase of higher education - in the second phase

of higher education - the concept of the concept of assimilation is closely linked to the concept of research activities. The success of research activities in the graduate of the master: ensures availability:

1) research activities - curiosity, interest in creative approach, the pursuit of the pursuit of the work, the pursuit of the work, the importance of creative activity, the effort of creative activities, and the perfection of creative activities;

2) creativity of thinking - the ability to promote ideas, the variances, the independence, critical thinking analysis of approaches, critical thinking analysis of approaches, critical thinking analysis of approaches.

3) the skills to study research and creating copyright methodology for research activities, and technology to create a comprehensive methodology of research and technology [4, 122- b.].

The success of the formation of research competencies that ensures the readiness of graduate graduates to research activities in many respects are determined by the introduction of the principles of individual-oriented education in the course of study. This is based on the development of each person's self-worth, individual, identity, as an individual, which has its unique subject experiences.

The essence of the person's directional approach is related to the two directions:

- The fact that the relations of teachers are directed to the establishment of an individual education model;

- Creating the learner as a subject of the educational process and to establish a study process in accordance with its personal qualities and experience.

In addition, the use of individual-oriented education involves the use of active and problematic educational methods in the pedagogical process. This will maximize the student to attract educational activities, which is very important in the master's level. Master's should learn solutions independently in developing its research abilities in problematic situations.

Approaches considered on masters Training system are expected to replenish the approaches with a synergetic approach.

According to the theory of pedagogical caterers, the Uzbek-provisions of the scientific systems are characterized by the self-organizing principles, laws of any self-organizing system, or the weakness and balancedcity.

The system of masters should be open, non-led and unbalanced, then forever, it will be effective, but also developing. The openness of the training system of masters depends in many ways to adapt quickly to its innovation, a changing information and development space, the use and development of modern educational technologies. The implementation of individual education in line with alternative strategies implies that the pedagogical process will not be linear. The continuous variation of labor market and the country's economy, the requirements of employers and science leads to the balanced state of masters training system.

Construction of the model in accordance with the principles of syneric approaches will take place in a series of stages. Initially, the bifurcation points, which include choosing one of the following subsequent education strategies, the next stage includes the pedagogical process and sustainable development, involving participational skills for the international development. In the next stage, it is necessary to create new imbalances on a certain order, after which the recipients need to change the educational trajectories. Thus, the training of masters is distinguished by the circumstances of the decision.

The fruits of the bratient training system is that the sum of all components in its accurate and logical system will yield more.

It is necessary to follow certain principles, which reflect the main doamic requirements for the preparation system of the object of the object. Systems, variations, predictions, flexibility, science, integration, stratification, consistency, and similar principles.

1. The principle of systemic principle is that the dynamic model is interrelated and presented as a single system of complement elements. The change in the status or functions of one of the elements leads to a change in the whole system. When

entering the new item or removing one of the available items, it is necessary to analyze and account for all possible consequences and effects.

2. The principle of optionality means that the model has different options in the model, which ensures the illegal and dynamics of the model.

3. Prophetic is the designation of the model to be accurate result, in our study is the formation of research competitions as a base in preparing these masters.

4. Principhurism Principhurism - The dynamic model of the training system should be built in this way that it should be possible to quickly change both the educational program and the educational goals and technology.

5. The principle of scientific activity is all elements of the model, in the process of study, is used to the use of innovative technologies and tools.

6. The principle of integration is the existence of a system that makes the system that affects the choice of necessary relations between components. In the creation of a dynamic model of the training system of primary education, integration is also used to create a single educational environment, which will create constant and comprehensive educational impact on the student.

7. The principle of stratified education is the ability to highlight micromodels that have similar characteristics within the model, but are able to operate in variable conditions.

8. Beacher principle - the elements of the dynamic model of training systems in primary education should be built on the basis of a logical structure, each of which is based on previous jars, taking into account its experience and features.

Thus, the integration of the provided methodical approaches, as well as the principles of development of primary education system, increases its efficiency and establishes its theoretically methodological basis for the development of the dynamic model of primary education.

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